

Introduction: This project aims to advance lunar In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) for oxygen production. Among various ISRU techniques, molten salt electrolysis (MSE) of regolith stands out for its efficiency, having proven its ability to extract 40-45 wt% of regolith feedstock as oxygen. [1] However, significant maturation of the process is required to achieve adequately pure oxygen as a product.

The gas exhausted from a MSE unit may consist of many gaseous substances that must be separated from the desired product of pure oxygen, for both life support and fuel applications. Besides oxygen and an inert carrier gas, the presence of other gaseous compounds are expected, such as volatiles embedded in the regolith and products of competing chemical reactions within the cell. The impact of even minor levels of contaminants may pose problems downstream.

Previously, two sets of gas samples from other external cells were analysed using our mass spectrometer, but ultimately the results were found to be inconclusive and hampered by contamination [2]. As a consequence, we decided to build our own MSE cell so that it can be in line with gas processing and gas analysis.

MSE cell construction: The constituents of the exhausted gas mixture from an MSE cell must be identified before creation of a purification regime. To this aim, we have designed and begun the construction of our own cell, capable of reducing regolith or simulant samples of up to 100g. A 150mm-tall, 80mm diameter crucible constituting the cell is enclosed in a vessel placed into a tabletop furnace. The furnace's heating is bolstered by supplementary resistance wire surrounding the crucible itself, contributing to maintaining the operating temperature of 950°C. The entire apparatus is maintained under a fume hood and water-cooling system for the upper part of the vessel.

Experiments: We will run experiments with the MSE cell and an exhaust line leading into a mass spectrometer (or gas sample container). The gas produced during an experiment can then be analysed on an experiment-by-experiment basis, with full creative control. Some of the planned experiments so far include testing different feedstocks (simulant, regolith, individual minerals, different carrier gases and their flow rates, and varying voltage relative to the decomposition voltage of the salt.

Future: Following analysis of the data from the cell experiments, a combination of gas purification techniques can be formulated, targeting the gaseous compounds thus identified, in order to produce an oxygen stream that satisfies the required purity levels

for breathing and use as a propellant. It is expected that such a regime will chiefly include apparatuses for filtration, distillation and sorption processes.

Alongside the processes outlined, a thermodynamic analysis of the system presented in our MSE cell is being conducted, in order to estimate what to expect from, and look for, in the results of the mass spectrometry.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge (B. Lomax) and Metalysis Ltd. (T. Johnson, I. Mellor) for collaborating on previous results during this project, presented at ELS 2024.

References:

[1] Lomax B. A. et al. (2020) *Planet.Space.Sci.* 180, 104748..

[2] Chopra A. et al (2024) *European Lunar Symposium 2024*